

Annotation Guideline for Noisy Comments Labeling

Introduction

High-quality code review comments are essential for automating the code review process. This study aims to explore the feasibility of automatically distinguishing between valid and noisy comments. To this end, we conduct manual labeling for review comments from open-source projects to understand the ratio of noise and facilitate further model development.

Objective

The primary objective of this study is to identify and remove noisy comments from original reviewers. This ensures that only relevant, clear, and constructive comments from reviewers are provided to models for training and evaluation purposes. Our goal is to label each review comment in a subset of sampled comments as either valid or noisy.

Definitions

Valid Comments: A comment is considered "valid" if given the input information (i.e., code diff for the code-to-comment task), it is possible for you to understand the rationale for the related output. This means you can understand what the reviewer's comment refers to (i.e., what the problem in the submitted code diff spotted by the reviewer is). Furthermore, when a comment is valid, it usually specifies the types of changes, including:

- Changes are needed to **refactor** the code to improve its quality;
- Changes are needed since **tests** for this code must be written;
- Changes are needed to better align this code to good **object-oriented design principles**;
- Changes are needed to **fix one or more bugs**;
- Changes are needed to improve the **logging** of its execution;
- Changes are needed for **other reasons** not listed above.

Noisy Comments: A comment is considered "noisy" if it is impossible even for you to understand the reviewer's comment. This includes the following types of noisy comments:

- **Unclear comment**: What the reviewer's comment is asking the developer to do is unclear. This could be because the comments are vague or irrelevant to code improvement.
- **Wrong linking**: the review comment is not relevant to the provided code diff.
- **No change asked**: the reviewer's comment does not request any change;
- **Contributor's comment**: the comment is from developers, used for self-justification

- Noisy for **other reasons** not listed above.

Task Description

You will be presented with:

1. Source code in the '**code diff**' column: This could be a code difference being submitted.
2. A reviewer's comment in the '**msg**' column: Feedback provided by the code reviewer.
3. Your task is to judge whether the msg is Valid or Noisy in the quality label column.
Please leave notes in the note column if you are unsure and explain why.